

**British Heart Foundation
Data Science Centre**

Led by Health Data Research UK

Ensuring phenotyping algorithms using national electronic health records are FAIR

Meeting the needs of the cardiometabolic research community

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1 Summary

Phenotyping algorithms enable the extraction of clinically-relevant information (such as diagnoses, prescription information, or a blood pressure measurement) from electronic health records for use in research. They have enormous potential and wide-ranging utility in research to improve disease understanding, health, and healthcare provision. While great progress has been achieved over the past years in standardising how genomic data are represented and curated (e.g. VCF files for variants), phenotypic data are significantly more fragmented and lack a common representation approach. This lack of standards creates challenges, including a lack of comparability, transparency and reproducibility, and limiting the subsequent use of phenotyping algorithms in other research studies. The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship¹ state that digital assets should be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable, yet the current lack of phenotyping algorithm standards means that phenotyping algorithms are not FAIR. We have therefore engaged with the community to address these challenges, including defining standards for the reporting and sharing of phenotyping algorithms. Here we present the results of our engagement with the community to identify and explore their requirements and outline our recommendations to ensure FAIR phenotyping algorithms are available to meet the needs of the cardiometabolic research community.

2 Background

Electronic health records (EHR) are data that are generated and captured during routine interactions across the healthcare system. Data contained within EHR has massive potential to improve healthcare, through research to develop new and improved treatments, increase understanding of disease incidence and progression, or by providing information to inform management of healthcare resources. Large-scale health research is dependent on computational methods and tools to extract clinically relevant information from structured information in EHR. This clinically relevant information, often referred to as *phenotypes*, could include any observable or measurable trait or characteristic of an individual, such as disease diagnoses (e.g. type 2 diabetes, ischaemic stroke, or prostate cancer), health-related risk factors (e.g. smoking status or alcohol consumption), or measurements of biomarkers (e.g. height, blood pressure, blood glucose, or body mass index (BMI)). Computational instructions that use the information contained in EHR to determine an individual's phenotype are often called *phenotyping algorithms*.

Phenotyping algorithms enable large-scale and efficient analysis, with wide-ranging utility in any study involving analysis of human phenotypes, including population-based observational studies, clinical trials, and large-scale omics studies. To ensure such research is interpretable and reproducible, and to maximise the potential of phenotyping algorithms in further research, they must be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR)¹. Ideally, algorithms defining the full spectrum of phenotypes to meet researchers needs should be available via a central accessible repository, in a community agreed standard format, that includes data and metadata to support the needs of users. While there are several resources designed to store and share phenotyping algorithms, including the HDR UK Phenotype Library², GA4GH PhenoPackets³, OpenSAFELY OpenCodelists⁴, PheKB⁵ and the

¹ Wilkinson, M. D. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci. Data* **3**, 160018 (2016).

² <https://phenotypes.healthdatagateway.org/>

³ <http://phenopackets.org/>

⁴ <https://www.opencodelists.org/>

⁵ <https://phekb.org/>

OHDSI Phenotype Library⁶, there is no community agreed or accepted standard or repository that fully meets these needs. The lack of a standard and multiple repositories creates challenges, including a lack of comparability, transparency, and reproducibility, and limits the subsequent use of algorithms in other studies and different use cases.

A major aim of the BHF Data Science Centre is to enable cardiovascular researchers to fully utilise electronic health data for research by developing, evaluating, and curating computable phenotyping algorithms in an efficient and reproducible manner. These phenotyping algorithms will be designed to meet the needs across our thematic areas. This includes definitions for phenotypes derived from structured data contained in electronic health records, imaging, and personal monitoring data, to be used in research including population-wide observational research, research cohort studies and clinical trials, and to answer research questions that may incorporate phenotypes outside the cardiometabolic area. Our *overarching aim* is, therefore, to make available phenotyping algorithms using a disease-agnostic standard, that are FAIR, and meet the needs of the diverse research community both nationally and internationally.

To identify the needs across our thematic areas we identified stakeholders with use cases involving phenotyping algorithms. We then carried out a series of interactive sessions to engage representatives from these stakeholder groups and identify and document their requirements (e.g. identify the key algorithm metadata fields that a user group deemed required for evaluating and reusing an algorithm). We outline our recommendations to:

- Ensure FAIR phenotyping algorithms are available to meet the needs of the cardiometabolic research community.
- Increase sharing of phenotyping algorithms

3 Workshops

3.1 Workshop organisation

3.1.1 Stakeholder and use case identification workshop

To identify stakeholders and phenotyping algorithm use cases from the cardiometabolic research community, we carried out an online interactive workshop (including 15 participants). The workshop brought together representatives across the thematic areas of the BHF Data Science Centres, including the associate directors leading each thematic area, research project managers and health data scientists. During the workshop we explored who in the cardiometabolic research community needs to use phenotyping algorithms, what they need to use them for and why. We also discussed what might be missing to enable them to do this. A virtual whiteboard tool (Mural) was used to capture input during the workshop, screenshot included in **Appendix A**.

3.1.2 Requirements gathering workshops

To establish the requirements to meet each of the use cases, we carried out a series of further online workshops to engage the key stakeholder groups identified. Each of these workshops included an introductory session with presentations on the BHF Data Science Centre and our aims, phenotyping algorithms and their relevance to the workshop participants and outlining the goals of the workshop. This was followed by an opportunity for participants to ask questions and interactive sessions to gather input from the workshop participants, with reporting back after each session, and a closing discussion session.

⁶ <https://github.com/OHDSI/PhenotypeLibrary>

We ran three of these requirements gathering workshops: one for health data researchers (including 5 participants) in December 2022 and two for clinical trials researchers (including a total of 19 participants) in January and February 2023. The workshop involving clinical trials researchers also formed part of the Standardising Clinical Outcome measures in Routinely-collected Electronic healthcare systems data (SCORE-CVD) programme of work². We engaged with each of these groups in separate workshops due to the differing background familiarity and language used (e.g. phenotype vs outcome measure), enabling us to tailor the workshop introductory material to meet the group's needs.

3.2 Stakeholders and use cases

In our initial workshop we explored who in the cardiometabolic research community might need to use or access phenotyping algorithms. Researchers were identified as the main users of phenotyping algorithms. However, it was recognised that researchers could be divided into two groups with distinct needs and levels of understanding:

1. Researchers who have some experience or familiarity with EHR data analysis, computer programming, and the term “phenotype” e.g. data scientists.
2. Researchers with little or no data analysis or coding experience, who are less familiar with the term “phenotype”. It was noted that this group is more likely to represent the majority of clinical trials researchers or healthcare professionals.

Several other stakeholder groups were identified who might have an interest in phenotyping algorithms, including patients and the public, data custodians, policy makers or funders. As the aim of this work is to ensure phenotyping algorithms meet the needs of the cardiometabolic research community, use cases of other stakeholders are outside the scope of this work. However, the need for grant award committees to review and understand the accuracy and reliability of a phenotyping algorithm is within the scope of this work, as researchers need grant award committees to be able to fairly assess funding applications.

The inputs gathered during the stakeholder and use case identification workshop were used to construct researcher use cases to describe what researchers need to access or use a phenotyping algorithm for and why. These use cases are listed in **Appendix B**.

3.3 Phenotyping algorithm requirements

To establish the requirements of the use cases we engaged with researchers and clinical trials researchers in a series of workshops. The interactive sessions focused on identifying participants' requirements in terms of:

- Finding/identifying phenotyping algorithms
- Knowing if a particular phenotyping algorithm meets their requirements
- Using or applying the algorithm
- Additional information required

Participants were asked to provide detail on the required data/metadata and resource functionality required to meet their needs, focusing on each of the areas above in turn. The Mural board screenshots from each of these workshops are shown in **Appendix C**. A list of all input gathered during the breakout groups is available in **Appendix D**.

We observed high levels of agreement in the input gathered and discussion across the different workshops and stakeholder groups (researcher and clinical trial researcher). All input and use cases gathered during these workshops were found to align with the use cases represented in **Appendix B**.

There was agreement on the functionality required to access phenotyping algorithms. Workshop participants wanted the phenotyping algorithms to be accessible in a single central open access repository. There should be a permanent DOI/accession ID for each phenotyping algorithm to enable users to cite and easily find a specific phenotyping algorithm. They wanted to be able to search by phenotype or outcome measure, with all phenotyping algorithms that define the search term being returned. After the search results had been returned, users wanted to explore and compare the returned phenotyping algorithms, and determine which best meets their needs.

It was felt that some of the information or metadata suggested for inclusion, would not be feasible for a researcher submitting a phenotyping algorithm to a repository to know, or would place an unnecessary burden on the submitter and discourage sharing. This included listing all publications that a phenotyping algorithm had been used in (other than their own) and listing all datasets that contain a particular code included in the code list. This information could potentially be curated by the repository or obtained by linking to or pulling in the information from other resources automatically through the use, potentially, of semantic tagging and searching.

The clinical trials researchers identified additional requirements to meet the specific needs of this community. This included information on any clinical trials the phenotyping algorithm has been used in. Due to the increased regulation of clinical trials compared to observational research, clinical trials researchers require additional detailed information on the accuracy and reliability of a phenotyping algorithm as evidence to support ethics or grant applications. The SCORE-CVD report⁷ highlights possible endorsement of phenotyping algorithms for use within trials; and initially this may be by the SCORE-CVD group which would incorporate clinical review, however, future endorsement could include recognised clinical societies, national bodies, and regulators.

There was agreement on the core information required to represent each phenotyping algorithm, including accurate and informative naming of the phenotype being defined, information on the publications the phenotyping algorithm has been used in, detailed information on the purpose of the phenotyping algorithm, how it was developed, used and any limitations. There was also agreement that detailed information is required on how the phenotyping algorithm has been validated and performance results including positive and negative predictive values, sensitivity and specificity. Information on how to apply the code list is essential, including a link to the data preparation and analytical code and any data pre-processing steps, with a proviso that this information should be understandable to users with limited coding experience.

There were several suggestions that it was felt could be deferred to a later date, for consideration as future extensions to a data standard or repository functionality. These include support for phenotyping algorithms defined by a clustering model or graph network, cross platform interfacing (e.g. translation of phenotypes and their components across nations) and better integration with the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model.

⁷ BHF Data Science Centre. *Standardising Clinical Outcome measures in Routinely-collected Electronic healthcare systems data (SCORE-CVD) Initial Report*. <https://zenodo.org/record/8171481> (2023)
doi:10.5281/ZENODO.8171481.

4 Recommendations

4.1 Recommendations

Here, we report our recommendations to ensure phenotyping algorithms are available to support the cardiometabolic research community and are FAIR. These recommendations are based on our community engagement, workshops and analyses.

1. Establish community agreement on a single, centrally accessible repository for phenotyping algorithms and methods, through promotion and engagement with the UK and international research community.
2. To support this, we report the following requirements:
 - a. Enable efficient storage of algorithmic data and metadata listed in **Table 1**. While recommendations for mandatory or recommended data have been included, we have not recommended a set of minimum data/metadata as we believe this should be defined as a result of wider community engagement to produce a community agreed standard format. We recommend that while the set of mandatory data and metadata elements in such a standard should support FAIRness and core use cases, the bar should not be set so high that it discourages sharing.
 - b. Develop functionality to support the use cases outlined in **Appendix B**. An essential part of this is supporting users to identify the phenotyping algorithm that best meets their needs. To facilitate this, we suggest implementing ontology supported searching, enabled by tagging each phenotyping algorithm with an appropriate overarching ontology term (e.g. SNOMED-CT) that best represents the phenotype being defined. We also suggest grouping the Phenotype Library entries that use the same core code list through a two-level user interface to display:
 - i. The core phenotype definition
 - ii. Submitted “uses” of these in a publication (“children” of i, above)
 - c. Provide documentation to support users accessing, using and submitting phenotyping algorithms. This documentation should be designed to support users with varying levels of background knowledge, previous experience and coding skills, and should include:
 - i. Developer and curator guidelines on what should be included in each of the metadata and data fields, with examples
 - ii. Dataset-specific implementation details such as clarification on whether all ICD-10 codes should be specified in code list or whether the inclusion of a code means that all sub-codes are included i.e. whether specifying I22 means codes I22.1, I22.2, I22.9 etc. are included
 - d. Develop and implement a semantic validation pipeline to be completed prior to upload. This will identify any syntax errors and ensure phenotyping algorithms shared in the repository are of high quality and contain all required data/metadata

The BHF Data Science Centre is committed to open-source science practices and will ensure all phenotyping algorithms developed or used as part of our research are shared with the community. We will encourage our researchers to annotate their phenotyping algorithms with the data and metadata outlined in **Table 1** and will advocate for enhancements to the Phenotype Library outlined in our recommendations, including storage of this data and metadata.

Table 1. Suggested data and metadata to be captured for each phenotyping algorithm.

Note: The Schema location corresponds to section of current HDR UK Phenotype Library schema (shown in **Appendix E**).

Key: Field highlighting:

green = already included in the Phenotype Library

orange = included in the Phenotype Library to some extent, but improvements are recommended

Cardinality:

0.* = zero to many

1..1 = exactly one

1..* = at least one to many

Required column values:

M = Mandatory, field is required

R = Recommended, field is not absolutely required as in some cases it might not be relevant

Schema location	Field	Mandatory/Recommended	Description	Cardinality
Phenotype definition	accession_id	M	Unique identifier	1..1
	title	M	Name/title of phenotype	1..1
	type	M	Type of phenotype e.g. disease or syndrome, biomarker	1..1
	primary_publication	M	Citation of primary publication, including title and authors	1..1
	primary_publication_link	M	Link to primary publication	1..1
	primary_publication_doi	M	DOI of primary publication	1..1
	publications	R	List of all papers published in, specified by DOIs and/or accession e.g. PubMed ID's	0..*
	ontology_term	M	Ontology term selected from specified ontology e.g. SNOMED to represent phenotype	1..*
	sex	M	List of sexes valid for the phenotype	1..2
	valid_event_data_range	M	Date range for events	1..1
	description_purpose	M	Purpose of phenotype e.g. what environment/use case was it intended	1..1
	description_developed	M	How phenotype was designed/developed	1..1
	description_used	M	How phenotype was used in primary study	1..1

Schema location	Field	Mandatory/ Recommended	Description	Cardinality
Phenotype definition	description_limitations	R	Any known or potential limitations	0..1
	description_inclusion_exclusion	M	Any population inclusion/exclusion criteria	1..1
	dataset	M	The dataset used to create the code list or that the code list was applied to	1..*
	dataset_id	R	DOI or or link to dataset	0..*
	dataset_type	R	Type of dataset e.g. research cohort vs routinely collected healthcare data	0..*
	dataset_country	R	Country of dataset used to create or apply code list	0..*
	creation_date	M	Date code list created/finalised	1..1
	primary_clinical_trial	R	Primary clinical trials used in with clinical trial reference e.g. ISRCTN or EuDRAC	0..*
	clinical_trials	R	List of any clinical trials used in with clinical trial reference e.g. ISRCTN or EuDRAC	0..*
	endorsement_approval_organisation	R	Name of endorsing or regulatory approval granting organisation	0..*
	endorsement_approval_date	R	Date of endorsement or regulatory approval	0..*
	regulatory_approval_study	R	Information on study approval was granted for (publication or clinical trial ref)	0..*
	validation	R	Method of validation e.g. genetic, case note review	0..*
	validation_description	R	Detailed description of any validation	0..*
	validation_publication_doi	R	Validation publication DOI, if published	0..*
	source_code	M	Link to source code	1..*
	logic	R	Representation of logic/psuedo code	0..*
	flowchart	R	Link to flowchart to represent any rules-based algorithm	0..*
	inclusion_exclusion	M	Any population inclusion/exclusion criteria	1..1
	quality_control	R	Description of any quality control/checking	0..*
data_preprocessing	R	Any cleaning or filtering carried out on the data prior to applying the code list that is specific to this phenotyping algorithm. This should include any boundaries/cut-offs applied by the researcher e.g. to numerical values or dates.	0..1	

Code list	coding_system	M	Coding system/terminology	1..1
	coding_system_version	M	Version or release date information for terminology	1..1
Code	code	M	Code/concept ID	1..1
	code_name	M	Clinical term associated with code	1..1
	code_position	R	Code position e.g. primary vs secondary in HES APC, diagnostic code positions	0..1
	code_type	R	Code type i.e. 0: Prevalent or Incident, 1: Prevalent Only	0..1

5 Acknowledgements

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We thank workshop participants for their engagement and rich contributions to the workshops.

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6 Appendices

Appendix A – Mural board image from stakeholder identification workshop

Appendix B - Key use cases identified

Researcher

- As a researcher I need to be able to understand the process and purpose that a phenotyping algorithm was created under/for so I can determine if it will help me complete my research
- As a researcher I need to find phenotyping algorithms that define the phenotype I am interested in so I can identify a phenotyping algorithm to use in my research
- As a researcher I need to determine if a particular phenotyping algorithm meets my needs (in terms of different algorithm characteristics (e.g. accuracy or resolution) from the data that is available) so I can determine if I can use it in my research
- As a researcher I need to understand how to best use a phenotyping algorithm so I can carry out the analysis required for my research study
- As a researcher I need to be able to create and curate a phenotyping algorithm following any best practices/standards if a phenotyping algorithm does not exist that meets my needs
- As a researcher I need to describe to a funding award committee which phenotyping algorithm(s) I will use and how I will use them within my research study to enable the grant award committee to assess my funding application or to report which algorithms I created post-award
- As a researcher I need to use a phenotyping algorithm to computationally identify from healthcare systems data how many/which people in the population/cohort have a particular phenotype to provide data for a research study or demographics on the population
- As a researcher I need to know which datasets a phenotyping algorithm requires/has been developed on so I know which datasets I require access to, so I can carry out my analysis
- As a researcher I need an accession ID or stable URL for the phenotyping algorithm I have used so I can reference it in my manuscript
- As a researcher I need to add phenotyping algorithms that I have developed to an open access resource so other researchers can find and use them
- As a researcher I need to obtain accession IDs for the phenotyping algorithms that I have developed and added to the resource so I can reference them in publications
- As a researcher I need a grant award committee to be able to review and understand the accuracy and reliability of a phenotyping algorithm to fairly assess my grant application

Clinical trials researcher

- As a clinical trialist/researcher I need to describe to the grant award committee how I will utilise a phenotyping algorithm and healthcare systems data within my clinical trial. The grant award committee must be able to review and understand how the data will be accessed and used in order to fairly assess my application.
- As a clinical trialist/researcher I need to use a phenotyping algorithm to computationally identify from healthcare systems data the demographics of the population e.g. how many people in a population meet a certain set of characteristics (e.g. has a particular phenotype, age range, date of presentation etc.):
 - to define recruitment parameters
 - ensure appropriate representation within the trial
 - to carry out feasibility analysis
- As a clinical trialist/researcher I need to use a phenotyping algorithm as an outcome measure to computationally identify possible participants for my clinical trial
- As a clinical trialist/researcher I need to use a phenotyping algorithm to computationally identify from healthcare systems data how many/which people in my clinical trial have

experienced a particular outcome to provide evidence for the clinical trial primary/secondary outcomes

- As a clinical trialist/researcher I need to use a phenotyping algorithm to computationally identify from healthcare systems data how many/which people in my clinical trial have experienced a particular outcome to compare against the same information gathered using traditional methods to validate the use of healthcare systems data
- As a clinical trialist/researcher I need to use a phenotyping algorithm to computationally identify from healthcare systems data which NHS trusts report accurate/complete health data required by this phenotyping algorithm and may be better placed to recruit for my trial
- As a clinical trialist/researcher I need to provide a reference for the phenotyping algorithm I used within my trial. For reporting I will require an accession ID or stable URL.

Appendix C – Mural board images from requirements gathering workshops

Researchers workshop – 19th December 2022

Phenotyping algorithms - requirements

What are your requirements of a phenotyping algorithm in terms of.....

Clinical trials researchers workshop - 30th January 2023

Phenotyping algorithms - requirements

What are your requirements of a phenotyping algorithm in terms of.....

Clinical trials researchers workshop - 2nd February 2023 (group A)

Phenotyping algorithms - requirements

What are your requirements of phenotyping algorithm in terms of.....

Knowing if it meets your

Using/applying the codelist

Information to meet any other needs

Clinical trials researchers workshop - 2nd February 2023 (group B)

Phenotyping algorithms - requirements

What are your requirements of a phenotyping algorithm in terms of.....

Appendix D – All input captured on Mural boards during requirements gathering workshops

Key:

Blue text - Identified in Researchers Workshop

Green text - Identified in Clinical Trials Researchers Workshops

* indicates that the suggested was made in multiple requirements gathering sessions

D.1 Finding/identifying

- *Clearly named and tagged
- Publication reference/ DOI or Universal resource identifier
- Links from Phenotypes to other ontologies e.g. MeSH, SNOMED CT
- Clinical trial reference – ISRCTN or EuDRACT
- Endorsement, date of review for clinical input (method to manage addition of new codes/clinical practice)
- *Ontology term to represent phenotype (support synonyms and child terms)

D.2 Knowing if it meets your needs

- *Description of purpose of phenotype
- *How phenotype was designed/developed
- *How phenotype was used in original study
- Phenotype diagnoses, purpose or outcome of interest
- When (date) it was developed
- Any known or potential limitations
- Ability to compare phenotyping algorithms and view differences between similar algorithms
- Ability to add feedback if not suitable for a given purpose
- *Endorsement/regulatory approvals (if granted)
- Details of any approval/endorsement committee
- Inclusion/Exclusion criteria (if applicable)
- Version and date of information standard used (already in phenotyping library)
- Information on which datasets codes can be located in, with a link to information on dataset coverage (UK wide?)
- Phenotypes that can be used internationally could be flagged

D.2.1 Validation

- Has this been validated by a clinician?
 - Guidelines for clinical/expert validation
- Details of any validation of the phenotyping algorithm (optional)
- Ability to validate in multiple datasets

D.3 Using/applying the code list

D.3.1 Phenotyping algorithm level information

- Population? E.g, only applicable to females over 60 years old
- Date limits of data that phenotyping algorithm was applied to e.g., any history or last 10 years? e.g.
<https://phenotypes.healthdatagateway.org/phenotypes/PH797/version/2221/detail/>
- Flowchart to describe rules based algorithm
- Population- Inclusion/Exclusion criteria (if applicable)

- Mapping files used if applicable

D.3.2 Code list level information (relating to each code list/concept within a phenotyping algorithm)

- Terminology
- Dataset
- Logic/pseudo code
- Example code of how code list and rules generate flags using dummy data
- All ICD-10 codes (parents and children)
- Quality-control rules communicated to users (e.g., handling the "." in ICD-10 and checking both 3-digit and 4-digit codes in HES APC)
- Flowchart to describe any rules based algorithm
- Link to source code (mandatory)
- Link to source code
- Has the data on which the codelist is being applied been cleaned or filtered?
- What data source was used to construct the code list – if the phenotype was developed using the limited GDPPR ref-set, then it might be missing codes that are available in, say CPRD

D.3.3 Code level information (relating to each code, within a code list)

- *Code position e.g. primary vs secondary in HES APC
- *Code type i.e. identifies prevalent only
- Diagnostic code positions
- Upper and lower limits for values.

D.4 Information to meet any other needs

- List of papers published in
- Prevalence/incidence numbers to aid with validation e.g., 10% of population have a history of x

D.4.1 Resource Functionality

- *Ontology supported searching
- *Ability to view similar phenotyping algorithms and compare differences
- Logs run on the clusters and compare against known code lists.

D.4.1.1 Validation of submitted phenotyping algorithm

- Terminology against terminology table

D.4.1.2 Documentation/guidance

- * Guidelines on data to be included for each field
- *Clarification between the concepts "phenotype" and "concept" in HDR UK library
- Clarifying to users about the difference between the effect of dates in phenotype extraction and cohort extraction
- The difference between ICD-10 in different countries
- Silent rounding of long codes e.g. guidance in documentation to not use software that rounds codes
- Information on any changes in the gold standard for validation

D.4.1.2 Suggestions to consider for later stage

- Any clustering-based definitions/rules (phenotypes defined by clustering model or graph network rather than code list and logic)
- Some sort of graph network
- Cross-platform (e.g. TRE<->SAIL) phenotyping (i.e., interfacing)
- Do we need to think-ahead about OMOP for future inter-operability of phenotypes?

Appendix E - Phenotype Library schema

(see https://phenotypes.healthdatagateway.org/about/hdruk_about_technical_details)

